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ABSTRACTS

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Examining the evolutionary toxicity of zinc oxide (ZnO) and copper oxide (CuO) nanoparticles on *Drosophila melanogaster*

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Abstract: Insects are one of the major causes of infectious diseases. The major insect vectors fall under the category of Dipterans, and act as agents for emergence and re-emergence of viral diseases, globally. The purpose of the current study was to ascertain whether nanoparticles can be used as potential insecticidal agents, especially to control the Dipterans. *Drosophila melanogaster* was chosen as the model organism for this study. The larvae were fed with sub-lethal concentrations of Zinc oxide (ZnO) NPs and Copper oxide (CuO) NPs orally and were allowed to develop to the adult stage. The effect of these NPs on the development and reproductive functions of the organisms were evaluated. The NPs exhibited a negative impact on the development or reproductive functions of the organism. The NPs were ingested by *D. melanogaster* which resulted in significant morphological changes in the organism and in its subsequent generation. The lifecycle and the survivability of *D. melanogaster* was also significantly reduced. Further molecular characterization of the effect of NP and its evaluation on other members of the Dipteran family will be relevant to develop these as potential agents for vector control.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Potential insecticidal, ZnO, CuO, Morphological changes

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